

THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

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Abstract. *This article presents a brief theoretical review of research on active and collaborative learning as multi-vector psychological training in education. Definitions of these learning forms are given. The main features of active and collaborative learning forms are listed. Types of learning activities used in collaborative learning are listed: discussion, peer learning, problem solving, joint writing, games. Possible reasons for the effectiveness of collaborative learning are indicated: socio-psychological factors and the ability to provide a high level of cognitive involvement.*

Keywords: *Psychological training, education, active learning, collaborative learning, small group teaching, educational psychology, pedagogical research.*

TA'LIM DASTURI ASOSIDA TALABALARNING KOLLABORATIV KO'NIKALARINI OSHIRISHDA KO'P VEKTORLI YONDASHUVLARNING PEDAGOGIK METODLARGA VA PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARGA BOG'LIQLIGI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola ta'limda ko'p vektorli psixologik treninglar faol va hamkorlikda o'rganish bo'yicha tadqiqotlarning qisqacha nazariy sharhini taqdim etadi. Ushbu o'quv shakllarining ta'riflari berilgan. Faol va hamkorlikda o'qitish shakllarining asosiy xususiyatlari sanab o'tilgan. Hamkorlik bilan o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan o'quv faoliyati turlari sanab o'tilgan: munozara, tengdoshlar bilan o'rganish, muammolarni hal qilish, birgalikda yozish, o'yinlar. Birgalikda o'qitish samaradorligining mumkin bo'lgan sabablari ko'rsatilgan: ijtimoiy-psixologik omillar va kognitiv ishtirokning yuqori darajasini ta'minlash qobiliyatini oshiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Psixologik trening, ta'lim, faol o'rganish, hamkorlikda o'rganish, kichik guruhlarda o'qitish, ta'lim psixologiyasi, pedagogik tadqiqotlar.*

ЗАВИСИМОСТЬ МНОГОВЕКТОРНЫХ ПОДХОДОВ ОТ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ НАВЫКОВ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ПРОГРАММЫ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлен краткий теоретический обзор исследований многовекторной психологической подготовки, активного и совместного обучения в образовании. Даны определения этих образовательных форм. Перечислены основные характеристики активной и кооперативной форм обучения. Перечислены виды учебной деятельности, используемые при совместном обучении: обсуждение, взаимное обучение, решение проблем, совместное письмо, игры. Показаны возможные причины эффективности совместного обучения: социально-психологические факторы и повышение способности обеспечивать высокий уровень познавательного участия.*

Ключевые слова: *Психологическая подготовка, образование, активное обучение, обучение в сотрудничестве, обучение в малых группах, психология образования, педагогические исследования.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of modern education requires the use of various models of classes that promote the activation and intensification of cognitive activity, the improvement of skills in independent search for solutions, research activities, and discussion. Active learning is the most effective in achieving these educational goals. Active learning is a process in which students develop higher-order thinking skills (analysis, synthesis, evaluation) through various types of educational activities (discussions, the method of concept maps, practical projects, group learning). In other words, active learning is any action related to the learning process other than simply viewing, listening, and taking notes. Active learning assumes that students are actively or experimentally involved in the learning process. Active learning, in a broader sense, is a way in which students purposefully seek to improve their understanding of content as well as expand their metacognitive and self-regulatory skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Active learning requires students to be dynamic participants in their learning, which involves:

- *Using complex learning strategies;*
- *Seeking deep conceptual understanding rather than superficial knowledge;*
- *Using learning strategies that have personal relevance;*
- *Using self-regulated and metacognitive strategies;*
- *Trying to share personal perspectives;*
- *Trying to understand the perspectives of others;*
- *Showing curiosity, interest, and enthusiasm.*

Most active learning strategies fall into three categories: collaborative learning, cooperative learning, and problem-based learning.

RESULTS

Collaborative learning and cooperative learning are similar methods that focus on the importance of interaction between students - members of a small group. The goal of collaborative and cooperative forms of learning is the transition of learning from individual learning activities to inclusion in a group form of organizing learning. Regarding the definition of the concepts of "cooperative learning" and "collaborative learning", there are both interpretations that emphasize their differences, and a definition according to which "collaborative learning is a term that unites many educational approaches that involve joint intellectual efforts of students united in groups of 2 or more people to search for explanations, solutions and create an educational product". In this paper, the term "collaborative" learning will be used in its unifying meaning. The collaborative process should have the following properties. Firstly, it is a thoughtful design. Lack of specific instructions and structure can cause difficulties in achieving learning objectives. High quality learning is ensured by setting specific learning tasks. The second feature of collaborative learning is collaboration. In collaborative learning activities, all group members must actively work together to achieve the goals. That is, if one group member does all the work, it is not collaborative learning. Regardless of whether all group members are given the same task or participants complete different tasks that together make up one large project, all students must share the workload. Third, learning must be meaningful, which implies a deep understanding of the topic, the ability to find connections between objects and phenomena, as well as the ability to relate new information to existing knowledge. Thus, collaborative learning is two or more students who work together and evenly distribute the workload as they move toward the intended learning outcomes.

In addition to these rather social and psychological aspects, two factors related to the cognitive sphere can contribute to the effectiveness of collaborative learning – the choice of a well-thought-out task and the level of mental effort required for the learning activity.

A learning task is an academic activity that the teacher purposefully plans, with specific instructions on what students should do in order to achieve the learning outcomes.

Well-thought-out tasks for collaborative learning motivate students to actively engage in the learning process.

Organizing collaborative learning can include planning various types of learning activities:

1) Discussion. The term “discussion” usually refers to teaching strategies that emphasize participation, dialogue, and two-way communication. In a broad sense, discussion is “a productive exchange of points of view, a collective exploration of problems”.

2) Peer Teaching.

This activity involves one student or a small group of students teaching others, who then do the same in return.

3) Problem Solving. These activities are based on the process of finding solutions to difficult and complex problems. Students typically seek to define a problem, find possible solutions, evaluate them, and then use one of the options to solve the problem.

4) Collaborative Writing is a special type of writing assignment designed to help students think through the content of the curriculum in pairs or small groups.

5) Games. In team-based academic games, students collaborate and compete to achieve a learning goal.

In addition to choosing a thoughtful task, the level of mental effort required to complete the task at the desired level can also enhance knowledge acquisition in collaborative learning. “Activity level” takes into account the level of students’ mental investment and the strategies they use to monitor their learning.

CONCLUSION

Active learning is a somewhat structured educational activity that increases the level of student involvement in the learning process. Collaborative learning is a proven method that helps students intensify the learning process both in terms of mastering the content of the curriculum and developing various thinking skills.

These pedagogical strategies have in common the promotion of a relatively high level of interaction between students. The effectiveness of collaborative learning is due to a combination of socio-psychological factors (improved quality of interpersonal relationships, psychological adaptation, positive attitude towards learning) and student participation in types of learning activities that promote cognitive involvement.

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